

LEXICAL AND SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HYPONOMIC RELATIONS AND ANALYZING ITS FEATURES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES.

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Annotation: *This article describes the lexical and semantic relation of hyponyms in English linguistics, which means that analyzing deeply the features of hyponyms and its characteristic features. One of the most vital progresses in cognitive understanding of information, one of the extremely significant devices to classifying vocabulary and performing of the human perception. Lexical and semantic relations of hyponyms are taken into consideration important when giving logical meaning and connection to speech that help to express the meaning of the word.*

Keywords: *hyponymy, hypero-hyponymic relation, lexical-semantic field, lexicon models, lexical unit.*

Introduction

In lexical classification, hyponymic relations of words, hierarchical structure of word combinations are considered important. Hyponymy is one of the types of systematic relations of units at the lexical-semantic level of language that is, gender-type, reciprocal, hypero-hyponymic relations. According to giving different views about this relationship in the lexical system of language, we rely on the facts that hypero-hyponymic relationships confirmed by many studies which belong to universal connections of lexical units. The main relationship of hyponymy is based on logical-semantic subordination that determines the hierarchical structure of individual semantic areas lexical system of the language as a whole, structuring the lexicon of the language.

The 21st century has been called the “age of multilingualism” by the European Union, and the problem of effective learning and teaching of foreign languages is becoming increasingly important. In particular, raising the intellectual potential of young people in Uzbekistan, gaining a wide range of knowledge and professional skills, as well as active communication with peers abroad, keeping abreast of all events, innovations and changes in the world today, is the most important condition for acquiring great intellectual wealth. Great opportunities have been created for them

to study foreign languages in depth. Like many other countries in the world, Uzbekistan pays special attention to the teaching and learning of foreign languages as a social direction of the state. There is every opportunity to keep abreast of the news¹. Also the President of Uzbekistan Mirziyoev Shavkat Miromonovich mentioned;- "It is time to create a new system of teaching foreign languages. This system must become a solid foundation for the future. Since we set ourselves the goal of building a competitive state, from now on, graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities must be fluent in at least two foreign languages. This strict requirement should become the main criterion for the work of the head of each educational institution"².

Literary review

Hyponymy is a less studied category in various systematic languages and has been considered in the scientific work of a number of researchers. The followings can be seen in the study of the problem of hyponymy in the work of scientists. To this time, many foreigners linguists investigated on many branches of language for instance, semantic and lexical characteristics of hyponymy that has been argued in their scientific research works which were illustrated many precious ideas and opinions. We can observe that the issue of hyponymy has been engaged in study about this in the works of the following linguists: Finch. G "Linguistic terms and concepts", Firth J.R "Modes of meaning", Cherry N "On Human Communication", Bierwish B.M "Semantics and Translations", Palmer F.R "Semantics", O'Grady W, Katamba F. "Semantics and Pragmatics", "The Analysis of Meaning" and Charles W.Kreidler "Introducing English Semantics". Also, the candidate of Philological Sciences, Associate Professor Doctoral student of the National University of Uzbekistan (DSc) Sabirova N.K mentioned some scientists' work which were connected to investigate hyponymy relation in her article "The Lexical and Semantic Relation of Hyponym"³.

¹ . Babajonova. D. New opportunities for learning foreign languages in Uzbekistan. Current research journal of history.2(6). 2021. P. 43-48.

² . On May 6. 2021. President Shavkat Mirziyoev Miromonovich's speech in a meeting on measures to improve the system teaching foreign languages. <https://www.google.com/https://yuz.uz/en/news/prezident>

³ Bierwish B.M "Semantics and Translations". UK:SIL Britain. 1970.

Palmer F.R "Semantics". Cambridge University press. 2000

O'Grady W, Katamba F "Semantics and Pragmatics", "The Analysis of Meaning".England:Pearson Ltd. 2011.

Charles W.Kreidler "Introducing English Semantics". London. 1998

Дяченко Л.Д. Гипонимия в системе английского глагола. Автореф. дисс. ...канд. филол. наук.- Москва. 1976.-30 с.

Lyons J. Semantics (2 vols). Cambridge University Press, 1977.

Katz J.J. Semantic theory. New York. Harper and Row. 1972

Lehrer A. Semantic fields and lexical structure. Amsterdam. North Holland.1974.

Murphy M.L. Semantic relations and the lexicon. Cambridge University Press. 2003.

Сафарова Р. Гипонимия в узбекском языке. Автореф. дисс. ...канд.филол. наук. – Ташкент, 1990.-13 с.

It can be observed that the phenomenon of hyponymy was more studied in the noun category. If representing a hyponymic relation in the noun phrase, such as a type of *X is Y*, the structure in which *X* is used instead of *Y* in the sentence. This formula only requires the use of the noun part of the speech, for example, the meaning of the words “*dog and lion*” are part of the meaning of “*animal*” make sense but *not* “*animal is a kind of dog and lion*”.

Figure 2. Lexical hyponymic configuration of the noun “ *Animal*”

In this picture, a variety of meanings are observed in the hyponyms of the noun “*Animal*”. This noun has six hyponyms, all of which have a specific meaning. This kind of hierarchical structure of semantic area can be mostly made a scientific observation in hyponymy. They could be regarded from top to bottom, which means that higher level is more general and the lower is more specific. For instance, the word “*flower*” will be the highest level followed by *rose*, *lily*, *tulip* and the lowest level may comprise *garden tulips*, *parrot tulips* and *triumph tulips*.

Conclusion

The hyponym and hyperonym relationship is very important in giving a logical connection in speech, expressing the meaning of words. There is no clear basis for the fact that a hypero-hyponomic relationship is a linguistic-lexical relationship rather than a cognitive-semantic relationship. The taxonomies of hyponymy do not cover all types of relationships that fall into the general term. Also, it helps to avoid more repetitions in oral and written speech.

REFERENCES:

1. Babajonova. D. New opportunities for learning foreign languages in Uzbekistan. Current research journal of history.2(6). 2021. P.43-48. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.37547/history-crjh-02-06-10>
2. On May 6. 2021. President Shavkat Mirziyoev Miromonovich's speech in a meeting on measures to improve the system teaching foreign languages. <https://www.google.com/https://yuz.uz/en/news/prezident>
3. J. Dzhumabaeva, N. Sabirova. The study of hyponymic taxonomy in English linguistics and the lexical and semantic relations of hyponymy. Ilkogretim Online-Elementary Education Online,2020; 19(4):pp. 870-878. Doi:10.17051/ilkonline.2020.04.195